

**AZERBAIJAN REPUBLIC
PRODUCTION ASSOCIATION “AZERIGAZ”**

SOCAR202G00021630560046X0307G

03.07.2023

To the National Academy of Sciences of
Azerbaijan Director of the Institute of
Philosophy Professor I.R. Mammadzada

Regarding the provision of a review of the monograph

Dear Ilham muallim,

Your letter dated June 29, 2020, No. 51/01-80, concerning a review of the monograph “Gasification of Azerbaijan and Operation of the Gas Economy (1955–1970)” has been considered at the Production Association “Azerigaz”.

The monograph “Gasification of Azerbaijan and Operation of the Gas Economy (1955–1970)” was provided by the author of the monograph, A. Alizade, in written and video forms, and a response to it was sent on behalf of JSC “Azerigaz” by letter dated June 17, 2020, No. SOCAR202900021630560046X03079. As is known, by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, dated June 12, 2006, No. 1494, June 20 was established as the professional holiday of gas economy workers of the Republic of Azerbaijan (the text of the decree is attached). As stated in the preamble of the decree, this decision was made in connection with the 70th anniversary of the establishment of the gas economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan. On June 20, 2006, in a solemn ceremony with the participation of the First Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Ministry of Industry and Energy, the Confederation of Trade Unions of Azerbaijan, the State Oil Company of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Production Association “Azerigaz”, and other state institutions, the 70th anniversary of the establishment of the gas economy was celebrated. During the event, a number of individuals were awarded state honors, which was widely reported in the mass media and online resources.

As indicated in the review of the Production Association “Azerigaz”, with the creation of the “Azgaz” trust in 1936, regardless of subordination, centralized formation of the gas economy began from that time, along with the construction of gas supply networks and the gasification of the housing stock. These works, regardless of scope and subordination, began to be managed from a single center. This refers not to the creation of the “Azgaz” trust, the Main Gas Administration, or other institutions, but to the formation of the gas economy as a sector of the country’s economy. Undoubtedly, in subsequent periods, the management structure of the gas economy was repeatedly improved, and today the

Production Association “Azerigaz”, which manages the country’s gas economy, successfully continues its activities as a structural unit of the State Oil Company of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

It should be noted once again that this monograph, which utilizes archival materials, receives a positive evaluation in terms of its content and character. It would be more appropriate to present the monograph to readers as a publication of the Institute of Philosophy of the National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan. Other proposals mentioned in your letter may be considered in the future.

With respect,
General Director
Ruslan Aliyev

(Translation from Azerbaijani)